

Three Quantum Bound Probabilities and Entropy

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Given a single particle bound wavefunction, $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, it is traditionally stated that $W(x)W(x)$ is the probability to find a particle at x . We have argued that $W(x)W(x)$ is actually a resolution profile or a probability for interaction and does not indicate whether a particle is at x or not. (We discuss this briefly in the note.) It is linked to an observer trying to find the particle, on average at x , not if the particle is present there and interacting with $V(x)$. If one normalizes $\int dx W(x)W(x) = 1$, then it follows that $\sum_p a(p)a(p) = 1$. Thus, $a(p)a(p)$ has the appearance of a probability as well and one might argue that it is the probability to have a momentum p . The catch is that with $W(x)W(x)$ one considers spatial resolution/interaction without knowing p and with $a(p)a(p)$, one knows nothing about x .

Given $\exp(ipx)$, the probability for a free particle impulse hit at x , one knows both p and x and may use this probability to calculate $KE_{ave}(x) = \{\sum_p a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x)$. We note that this probability does not have 0 points when $W(x)=0$. It shows the particle does not avoid $W(x)=0$ points in internal interactions with $V(x)$, we argue. $a(p)\exp(ipx) / W(x)$ is a third probability. Given that it holds at a fixed x and ranges over p (it is sometimes called $P(p/x)$) it should be linked to $a(p)a(p)$, but it considers spatial issues. We suggest that it should be combined with $W(x)W(x)$ as this demonstrates resolution or measuring interaction hits and is linked to an external observer. The product probability, however, imposes the 0 points of $W(x)$. This simply means, we argue, that a person making measurements does not interact with the particle at these $W(x)=0$ points, not that the particle does not exist there. Using this probability, as we have shown before, yields an average of the Shannon's entropies created using $W(x)W(x)$ and $a(p)a(p)$ as probabilities. Here we try to understand the relationship between these three probabilities more closely without using the usual $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$, $P(p) = a(p)a(p)$ and $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W$.

Presence of a Quantum Particle

It is traditionally stated that:

$$W^*(x)W(x) \text{ (which is } W(x)W(x) \text{ for a quantum bound particle) } \quad (1)$$

represents the probability to find a particle at x . We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is the probability for a particle with momentum p to render an impulse hit at x and that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ freezes out motion and shows that interaction hits are the same for each dx . Given $W(x)W(x)$, they are not the same at each x , but rather give a profile which we argue represents average relative interaction hits at x . This should then be linked with an observer measuring a quantum particle at x through its interaction, but if $W(x)=0$ and $W(x)W(x)=0$, we argue that this does not mean that the quantum particle is not at x for which $W(x)=0$. First of all, the center-of-mass of the particle is not the same as the x found in $\exp(ipx)$ and secondly,

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{\sum_p a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x). \quad (2)$$

is not 0 even if $W(x)=0$. There is average kinetic energy at x even if $W(x)=0$. For an infinite well potential, $W(x)=0$ at $x=0$ and $x=L$, but there is still average kinetic energy and so pressure at the walls. The quantum particle seems to be present there, it is simply not being measured (on average) as being there. This is associated with a resolution pattern. Given

$$\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) = 2 \cos(px) \quad ((3))$$

which is used in bound state calculations, $\cos(px)$ shows the resolution pattern present. This pattern is linked with a wavelength \hbar/p which means one cannot have equal measurement hits at each x or one would not see the pattern. It does not mean that the particle does not exist at $\cos(px)=0$ points, we argue. As a result, $W(x)W(x)$ seems to be linked to measurements, but a measurement of $W(x)W(x)=0$ does not mean that the particle is not present at $x=0$. One uses:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

and so average kinetic energy linked with interaction is present even when $W(x)=0$, it is just that one does not measure it.

Three Probabilities

It seems that one has three probabilities present: $W(x)W(x)$ is a resolution or measurement interaction probability, but if it is normalized through

$$\int dx W(x)W(x) = 1 \quad \text{then} \quad \sum_p a(p)a(p) = 1 \quad \text{as well} \quad ((5))$$

This suggests that $a(p)a(p)$ might be the probability to have a momentum p . This is interesting as $W(x)W(x)$ includes all p values and $a(p)a(p)$ makes no reference to x . These two probabilities seem to be linked with measurements (made by an observer) and so one might write Shannon's entropies for each:

$$\int W(x)W(x) \ln(W(x)W(x)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_p a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p)a(p)) \quad ((6))$$

One could add the two entropies or add and divide by two to obtain an average value.

This begs the question: What does one do with the probability $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. This is used in the key calculation ((4)) (essentially the Schrodinger equation), but it is not a probability which one measures. Nevertheless, one might suggest that it is linked with a range of p values for a fixed x . This probability shows information about the spread of p and includes the $\exp(ipx)$ interaction probability, but does not show the x measurement resolution in the problem. If one is only interested in an interaction probability, one might use

$$a(p)\exp(ipx)/W \ln(a(p)\exp(ipx)/W) \quad ((7))$$

As we have shown in a previous note, however, one may multiply the probability $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ by $W(x)W(x)$, the resolution pattern. This means that if $W(x)=0$, the product is also 0 which means that the probability $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ associated with average motion has the resolution pattern (which loses information in x) imposed upon it. If one uses this probability, then

$$\sum_{p,x} a(p)\exp(ipx) W \ln(a(p) \exp(ipx) W) = .5 (W W \ln(W) + a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p))) + \sum_{x} W x d/dx W \quad \text{for } a(p) = a(-p) \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{Note } \sum_{x} W x d/dx W = \sum_{p,x} a(p)\exp(ipx) ipx = \text{constant} \quad ((9))$$

In other words, there is no more average information in $W(x)W(x)$ and $a(p)a(p)$ than in $W(x)W(x)$ and $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that three probabilities appear in a quantum bound problem, $W(x)W(x)$, $a(p)a(p)$ and $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. The first two are associated with measurements made by an observer with $W(x)W(x)$ representing a resolution pattern. We argue that $W(x)=0$ does not mean that the particle is not present at x , it is simply not interacting on average at that point with an observer. It can still produce interaction kinetic energy at that point linked to a $V(x)$. The third probability is used to find $KE_{ave}(x)$, i.e. $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. $KE_{ave}(x)$ is not 0 for $W(x)=0$ and shows that there is interaction kinetic energy even when $W(x)=0$. $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ involves x , but it is fixed. The range is over p . It does not make use of the resolution probability $W(x)W(x)$ as one considers not external measurement, but internal ones. If one wishes to consider both and multiplies $W(x)W(x)$ by $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W$, then one imposes the 0 points of $W(x)$. Creating a Shannon's entropy of this product yields $.5$ (Shannon's $W(x)W(x)$ + Shannon's $a(p)a(p)$) + constant as we have already shown in a previous note. Here, we try to understand the reason for this result more clearly. It seems that one does not have any more average information in $W(x)W(x)$ and $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W$ than in $W(x)W(x)$ and $a(p)a(p)$.